

Lightning Proceedings of NLP4DH and IWCLUL 2023

Mika Hämmäläinen, Emily Öhman & Khalid Alnajjar (eds.)

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Preface

Welcome to the joint NLP4DH (International Conference on Natural Language Processing for Digital Humanities) and IWCLUL (International Workshop on Computational Linguistics for Uralic Languages) event, a landmark event merging digital humanities with computational linguistics, emphasizing Uralic languages and wider linguistic variety. This year, we explore the intersection of NLP technology with humanities research, particularly in diverse language analysis.

IWCLUL continues to play a vital role in preserving Uralic languages through innovative computational approaches. Together with NLP4DH, it expands its focus on minority language preservation and development.

Our joint event highlights our commitment to interdisciplinary research and the importance of linguistic diversity. We offer a rich blend of innovative NLP applications and advanced Uralic language studies.

This collaboration opens new research and practical avenues, especially in under-researched languages. We thank all contributors, participants, and organizers for making this possible and look forward to the insightful outcomes and partnerships.

Join us in this unique celebration of linguistic diversity and interdisciplinary research, in partnership with SIGUR, ACL's Special Interest Group for Uralic Languages.

This proceedings contains work presented as lightning talks in the event.

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Exploring gendered differences in political speech: Female representation and legislative speech patterns through keyword-assisted topic modeling

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Introduction

Female representation is a question of pivotal importance. Many countries have introduced quotas for female candidates to increase the proportion of female legislators in elected assemblies. Still, in many countries like Japan, the number of female politicians is lagging. In 2023, only 9.7% of legislators in Japan's lower house and 22.6% of legislators in its upper house were women. In Japan's local assemblies, the proportion of women is just as low with only 10.4% of prefectural assembly members being women (Gender Equality White Paper 2023).

The lack of representation of women in assemblies raises significant concerns regarding the quality of democratic governance. It is widely known that female and male politicians tend to focus on different types of issues (see Dodson and Carroll 1991). One understudied question on the impact female representation however has been the impact female representation has on how legislative discourses and agendas are created in assemblies. Some studies have shown that women in systems where females are little represented, women tend to spend more time discussing issues that are more associated with women such as gender equality and childcare (see Unal 2021). However, what these studies do not focus on is how the relative representation of women affects how strongly women focus on these issues.

It has for example been explored that the lack of female representation in assemblies means that those few female legislators that are elected may feel obligated to focus on discourses that have traditionally been associated with women such as childrearing and elderly care (see Mansbridge 1999; Carroll 2003). This may impede their chances of participating actively in the debate in the assemblies. Furthermore, the lack of female representation can lead to many perspectives not being discussed in the assemblies which may decrease the overall diversity of debate in assemblies.

We expect that the lower the proportion of female legislators is, the higher the proportion is that females spend discussing these traditionally female associated discourses. On the other hand, the lower the proportion of female legislators, the lower the proportion of these discourses will be overall. Therefore, we expect that the proportion of female legislators will impact both the contents of female legislators' speeches but also the diversity of speech that occurs in the assembly overall.

Analysis

To test these hypotheses, we use a keyword-assisted topic model to analyze the contents of legislator speeches in assembly. Keyword-assisted topic modeling is a powerful tool which makes it possible to assign keywords to find out specific topic content in speeches (Eshima, Imai and Sasaki 2023). In the research, we look at whether female legislators tend to focus more on traditionally female-centric topics such as healthcare, education and social welfare (see Endo and Ono 2023) but also if the proportion of female legislators effect the extent to which women legislators tend to focus on these issues. Furthermore, we also look at how female representation impacts how much these topics are discussed by male legislators as well as in the assembly overall. We expect that

the increase of female legislators will decrease the proportion that female legislators focus on these issues but will increase the proportion of these topics overall.

Figure 1: Histogram of proportion of females in prefectural assemblies

We use the case of Japanese prefectural assemblies to test these claims. Japanese prefectural assemblies are useful for several reasons. Firstly, as we established above, prefectural assemblies have a very low proportion of female legislators which makes them an ideal case for exploring the effect lack of representation has on political discourse. Furthermore, the proportion of female legislators varies dramatically from legislature to legislature which means it is possible to explore the effects of representation comparatively. For example, in Tokyo metropolitan assembly in 2021, more than 30% of legislators were women. At the same time, in the Kumamoto prefectural assembly the percentage of women legislators were only 2.1%. As can be seen in figure 1, the proportion of women in prefectural is very diverse. This large disparity inside the same country is an almost unique opportunity to empirically test the effect of female representation inside the same country.

Our dataset includes data on legislative speeches made by

prefectural assembly members in 46 (out of 47) prefectures over the years 2002 – 2021. The data was scraped from the assembly minutes archives of prefectural assemblies. In total, our data includes over 180,000 speech documents made by over 5,000 politicians over four distinct electoral periods. The data also includes personal information on the politicians such as sex, party identification, number of times reelected, district magnitude, previous job experience etc. Furthermore, we include demographic information on prefectures such as population, urban population and proportion of elderly to control for demographic differences which may affect the speech contents in prefectural assemblies. The unit of analysis in the study is prefecture-electoral period.

Figure 2: Shows the relative change in topic appearance of topics which have traditionally been considered to be more “feminine” by female representation.

In conclusion, our study examines the critical issue of female representation in politics through the lens of Japanese

prefectural assemblies. We have highlighted the concerns linked to the underrepresentation of women in these assemblies, including the potential impact on diverse discourse and legislative agendas. Using keyword-assisted topic modeling, our preliminary findings suggest that as the number of female legislators increases, this has positive effects on the proportion of some female topics while a few topics were negatively associated. For male legislators, the increase of female legislators did not seem to affect the contents of their speeches at all. While our results are preliminary, this ongoing research illuminates the relationship between gender representation and political discourse. As we continue to refine our analysis and explore broader topics, we expect to find significant insights to the global conversation on gender equity in politics. We invite further discussion, collaboration, and inquiries from the audience as we work toward a comprehensive understanding of how female representation shapes legislative dynamics, ultimately aiming for more inclusive and representative political systems benefiting all citizens regardless of gender.

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Linguistic remix – Mapping the intertextual relationship of poetic texts with NLP tools

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Introduction

The aim of the project is developing an NLP tool that helps the quantitative analysis of intertextual relations between Hungarian poetic texts, and makes possible the corpus-based comparison of texts in the context of the theoretical framework of Remix Studies (RS). In studying the connection between texts, RS offers a new, complex perspective by interpreting linguistic practices ranging from micro-level linguistic phenomena to macro-level identity constructions. The project is based on the ELTE Poetry Corpus and ELTE Folk Song Corpus of the National Laboratory of Digital Heritage and the ongoing Lyrical Poetry Corpus project of ELTE DiAGram Research Centre for Functional Linguistics. In general, the research contributes to the understanding of linguistic creativity by revealing the patterns of text production.

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Linguistic remix

As a consequence of the technological changes of the 20th century, the boundaries between the producers and the audience have blurred, i.e. creation has increasingly emerged as a global, communal and collaborative activity (Lessig 2008: 28-31). It is therefore more relevant to understand the cultural practices and actors of the digital world in terms of participation and sharing, as opposed to the cult of genius that is based on the artistic ideal of Romanticism, which emphasizes individual invention. The emerging concept of remix culture (Lessig 2008) questioned and renegotiated not only the term of authorship, but also the fundamental understanding of creativity and culture. The study of these phenomena started in the 2000s and was fulfilled in the 2010s with the establishment of Remix Studies as a field of research. RS has developed into a complex field which links different disciplines by aiming to understand the creativity of the new media era (Navas – Gallagher – burrough 2021).

The concept of remix can be adapted successfully to the examination of cultural practices because – as Lessig points out – while the phenomenon of remixing may seem novel, its core mechanism has long been a part of human culture: remixing with (digital) media is identical to the fundamental process of language use. Evoking and incorporating the words of others into written works or conversations is so natural that we do not even notice the borrowing. Popular text generation tools which are based on the Large Language Models (LLMs) owe their success to the fact that they exploit this fundamental linguistic mechanism. These tools learn from large amount of textual data sets to determine the probabilistic values of linguistic patterns for generating textual content, in other words, they remix by recognising and regenerating existing linguistic patterns.

Method

Taking this into account, the main aim of the research is to understand better the creative potential of text production, i.e. to explore the networks of texts by adapting the concept of remix to linguistics research. This would be achieved by extending the functions of the ELTE DH corpora and the Lyrical Poetry Corpus. The ELTE Poetry Corpus of 3,441,864 tokens contains the complete poems of 50 Hungarian canonical poets, and the ELTE Folk Song Corpus of 148,524 tokens contains 2390 Hungarian folk songs. Besides tokenization, lemmatization, as well as the part-of-speech and morphological analysis, the automatic annotation of the structural elements (title, stanzas, lines) and the sound devices (rhyme scheme, rhyme pairs, rhythm, alliteration, phonological structure of words) of the poems and songs were completed in XML format (Horváth 2020a, 2020b).

During the development of the Lyrical Poetry Corpus, a corpus of 1.5-2 million words of poems by contemporary authors, slam poetry and song lyrics will be annotated using the automatic analysis procedures of the ELTE Poetry and Folk Song Corpus. By adding new functions to these corpora they will be connected to international projects such as Chicago Homer (Kahane – Mueller 2001), Tesseractae (Coffee et al. 2013) or Commonplace Cultures (Gladstone – Cooney 2020). These projects focus on the creative reuse of texts, intertextual relations, recurrent patterns, i.e. they facilitate the quantitative analysis of remix phenomena with the search and comparison function of the query interfaces of the corpora.

Following these models automatic syntactic analysis and vector representation of meanings will be added to the Hungarian corpora. The future tool is based on the mosaic n-gram method (Indig 2017) to extract patterns (trigrams of lemmas and POS tags) for comparing the texts. The mosaic n-grams not only help to find classic, literal cases of intertextuality, but are useful for exploring more abstract structural similarities of the texts as well. In the end of the project a multi-level annotated Hungarian poetry corpus will be available for intelligent searching and complex text comparison.

Summary

In summary, the project will conclude with the development of a method for exploring the network relations of poetic texts in Hungarian, as well as for quantitatively measuring the similarity of texts by extending the functionality of ELTE corpora. The identification of the linguistic patterns appearing in the texts also contributes to the better understanding of the Hungarian language structure. More generally, the exploration of the relationships between texts also helps developing a general model of language production, which brings us closer to the interpretation of cultural practices.

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Private ownership and profitability: the implications for social media data in digital humanities research

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Introduction

As social media platforms change ownership and pursue higher levels of profitability, this has an unintended impact for researchers and academics seeking to utilize social media data for research. With most prominent social media platforms holding their bases of operations in Silicon Valley, it is also important for digital humanities scholars interested in social media research to understand the culture that informs the decisions made in these companies. Several NLP studies have traditionally used social media data for analysis, although the future of this practice remains in flux as APIs change their levels of accessibility. Thus, this lightning talk concerns changes to social media platforms, the business model of social media companies, and the culture of Silicon Valley in order for researchers to better anticipate changes to access to data for research.

API changes

The issue of Application Programming Interface (API) changes are exemplified in the recent changes to two major social media platforms. Elon Musk's acquisition of Twitter, now called X, effectively removed Twitter as a source of data for digital humanities researchers. Elon Musk would cite the presence of bots on the platform as a reason for putting the API behind a paywall (Barnes, 2023). Previously, Twitter invited academic research in the forms of elevated access to their API with proper credentials, as well as access to datasets of identified disinformation campaigns for study. The Academic API access no longer exists under Musk's ownership, although the datasets on disinformation remain accessible. Moreover, Steve Huffman, CEO of Reddit announced in 2023 changes to Reddit's API that also placed it behind a paywall (Mehta, 2023). The changes to these two platforms mean that digital humanities research must adapt to changes in access to data.

Social Media's Business Model

The next topic of discussion for this lightning talk is the business model of social media companies themselves. In 2021, Mark Zuckerberg of Facebook, Jack Dorsey of Twitter, and Sundar Pichai of Google would have to testify before Congress concerning the functioning of their platforms and how it relates to disinformation on social media. In these hearings, members of Congress would question the ethics behind their business models (Edelman, 2021). Essentially, in order to maintain the illusion of "free" services, platforms aim to capture the most attention from users in order to mine data and sell better targeted ads.

Access to this data, and therefore, their levels of profitability, would take a hit following the entering of the EU's General Data Protection Regulation into force in 2016. Later in 2023, Zuckerberg would propose charging European Meta users for use of the platform to combat profit loss from lack of access to user's personal data, and the new subscription fee for European users of Facebook and Instagram was announced in October of 2023 (Njan, 2023). Putting social media APIs behind a paywall is just another attempt by social media companies to preserve their profitability, with unintended consequences for digital humanities researchers interested in utilizing social media data.

The Culture of Silicon Valley

The final topic of discussion relates to Silicon Valley culture, and the structure of funding for these social media companies. All major social media platforms have received venture capital funding, and the nature of venture capital explains why social media companies place profit over everything. Venture funding allows budding enterprises to operate at a loss before "going public," or in proper terms, before the enterprise's stock launch or initial public offering.

Steve Huffman in an interview with *The Verge* would comment on the controversy around placing Reddit's API behind a paywall stating, "whether we go public or not is separate from building a sustainable business or building a business that can stand on its own two feet. I love our investors, but I don't like depending on investors, and financial security is security" (Peters, 2023).

Reddit has yet to go public, but Twitter has been a public company since 2013. A common sense question revolves around why platforms like Twitter, which have achieved a level of ubiquity in daily use of social media, need to pursue higher profits and thus implement decisions like placing APIs behind a paywall.

The intricacies of Silicon Valley culture, with its focus on innovation and venture funding for entrepreneurs, has become an academic discipline within itself. Silicon Valley's structure of venture capital for budding companies has been explored in books like *The Rainforest: The Secret to Building the Next Silicon Valley* and courses at the Stanford d.school for engineers looking to start companies. Business model and culture is seen as integral to a "high-performance" company, or a company that is able to outperform 97% of other companies in relevant sectors (Nakajima et al., 2022).

Venture firms see their funding as part of a hierarchy of capital types that "nourish" the growth of the company (Wickham, 2015). The philosophy of venture capitalism entails a trade off: in exchange for amounts of funding into the millions of dollars, the expectation is that the company receiving the funding will scale in both size and profit. This is why social media companies will often add additional services to their platform as time goes on.

Implications

Changes to Twitter and Reddit's API reflect the drive for profits that can only be derived from user data because of their business models. Venture funding in both these companies mean that constant growth is expected from investors, and all these factors result in consequences for researchers intending to analyze phenomena on social media. As more and more regulation emerges around the use of user data, it is also expected that platforms may restrict more and more access for researchers. As APIs go behind paywalls, it is important to discuss the impact it may have on emerging and junior researchers who may not have the funding to pay for API access. Questions emerge for digital humanities researchers around the viability of social media data for research, despite the well-established impact of social media on daily life, mental health, and society.

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Unearthing Emotions: Analyzing Ancient Roman Inscriptions with NLP

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Introduction

The purpose of this project is to present a new method for the analysis of historical documents in historiography using methods from digital humanities and Natural Language Processing (NLP). Although hundreds of thousands of ancient Roman inscriptions have been digitized and published online by, e.g., the University of Heidelberg and the Sapienza University of Rome, private historical documents such as tombstones erected by individuals have not received much attention in previous studies due to their sheer volume. However, by utilizing NLP and emotion analysis techniques, it is possible to extract elements that have not been previously available to researchers of history.

We aim to show the geographical and chronological distribution of "emotions" in the texts of tombstones and their transformations and to clarify how people's attitudes shifted in the 1st-3rd centuries when most of the inscriptions were written.

Many of the tombstones in ancient Rome were placed by people of lesser social and legal status, such as freed slaves. Tombstones are the main source of information on the "emotions" of people of social classes who do not appear in history books, which are the main sources of Roman historical research, toward their family members and close relatives.

For the city of Rome and its environs, some studies have explored the sentiments of ordinary Romans towards their deceased children via an analysis of epithets (King 2000; McWilliam 2001; Nielsen 1997; 2019), but the epigraphic databases contain hundreds of thousands of inscriptions which were not included in such investigations. The fact that the inscription database contains not only texts but also metadata will allow us to clarify what expressions were used in what contexts and how they varied with time and place.

Cataloging this data extraction and visualizing the representations and differences will yield results that will provide new impetus for research fields such as ancient Roman social history, family history, emotional history, and mortality studies. In addition, the method of data analysis and the data set used in this study will serve as a basic tool for similar research in the future and will open up possibilities for the study of ancient Greek and Roman history using methods from digital humanities. In addition, while historical databases are well developed worldwide, the use of digital humanities research methods has not progressed at the same pace as the emergence and extension of these databases.

Data and Methods

Our first research focus is a more thorough understanding of the connection between parents of

young children and their relation to death. Specifically, uncovering previously hidden patterns and expressions that our quantitative methods will be able to discover.

Figure 1. Data repository: Epigraphic Database Heidelberg

The study of the history of emotion has attracted much attention in the fields of Greek and Roman studies in recent decades (e.g. Chaniotis & Ducrey 2014), particularly since the "Affective Turn" (Clough and Halley, 2007) that shifted the research focus in many humanities fields.

Most of the inscribed texts on Roman tombstones are composed containing some fixed recurring phrases, but others contain verses and original expressions related to emotions. The grief of bereaved family was shared with passersby, and it reflected the tradition and transformation within society (Dutsch 2008). Considering this, we have selected a few keywords such as "lacrima" (tears) and "memoria" (memory) as a potentially fruitful starting point for our analysis.

We have to date, regionalize, and pre-process the collected large amounts of data from multiple different databases and other sources (collected for previous projects, Epigraphic Database Roma, etc.) and extract some common expressions from the inscriptions in these data.

We use CLTK (Johnson et al., 2021), a toolkit for natural language processing of Latin (which gives part-of-speech information on words, etc., similar to NLTK by Bird, 2006) and Latin BERT (Bamman & Burns, 2020) to create contextual word embeddings (rather than static) and extract phrasal textual similarities to detect novel expressions used in similar contexts as phrases containing our keywords. We will continue our research to expand on this, aiming to construct a dataset that will enable more precise data extraction, including word form analysis.

As most NLP tools have been created for English and Latin is no longer a living language, both NLP tools and labeled training data for Latin are rare and not as actively developed as tools for modern languages. We expect to have to do robust quality control of the results and develop partly new tools for Latin specifically as part of this project.

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Information Loss and the Transcription of Pre- Modern Japanese

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Introduction

Several OCR tools and transcription platforms have emerged for use with pre-modern Japanese texts. These include *Kuronet* and *Miwo* developed by the Center for Open Data in the Humanities (CODH), *Fuminoha* and *Komonjo Kamera* developed by Toppan, and *Minna de Honkoku* developed by researchers at the University of Tokyo, Kyoto University, and the National Museum of Japanese History.

The decisions made in the development of these tools shape transcriptions and the information included therein, as well as the transcription process. In this lightning talk, I will discuss the loss of information across different transcription platforms.

Differences between Tools

Tools accessible to everyday users offer different features which influence user experience and the transcription process. *KuroNet*, *Miwo* and *Komonjo Kamera* offer full-text OCR services, whilst *Minna de Honkoku*, which requires users to perform and input the transcription manually, provides a text recognition tool for single characters only. *Miwo* and *Komonjo Kamera* allow users to transcribe materials photographed through their device's camera, whilst *KuroNet* and *Minna de Honkoku* are confined to texts that exist in IIIF format and in the case of the latter hosted on one of the site's projects. Other issues relate to cost, speed, and how data is used or shared.

Feature	<i>KuroNet</i>	<i>Miwo</i>	<i>Komonjo Kamera</i>	<i>Minna de Honkoku</i>
Character Recognition	Full-Text OCR	Full-Text OCR	Full-Text OCR or Single Character	Single Character Recognition Tool
Compatible Texts	IIIF Images	Printed Materials	Printed or Handwritten Materials	IIIF Images hosted on projects
Data	User Access Only	User Access Only	Shared with Company	Published as Open Access
Speed	Instant	Instant	Instant	Timely
Price	Free	Free	Paid	Free

Table 1: Overview of Tool Differences

Information Loss

In addition to these overarching differences are decisions made by developers to include or exclude certain information from the transcription of a text. *Minna de Honkoku* is the best platform for limiting information loss. Users are required to transcribe all features of the text including interlinear glosses such as *furigana*, different markers (*kunten*, *kaeriten* etc.) used to guide the reader of certain texts, and text that appears as part of images. If text appears in non-Japanese script this can also be input into the system. The primary loss of information is produced by transcription rules which require users to input modern *kanji*. This means that older and variant forms are not captured within a transcription. Conversely due to technological limitations *KuroNet*, *Miwo* and *Komonjo Kamera* do not consistently transcribe interlinear gloss, markers, non-Japanese script, or rare characters, and struggle with text embedded in images. Use of these tools, therefore, excludes the possibility to ask certain research questions about the use of interlinear gloss, non-Japanese scripts etc. Furthermore, key parts of the text may be lost in cases when features such as gloss are crucial to the meaning of the text (in the case of puns, for example).

Accuracy

All tools offer disclaimers about the accuracy (or potential inaccuracy) of transcriptions. *Minna de Honkoku* contains potential fail-safes in so far as transcriptions are reviewed by other users and its AI character recognition tool offers only suggestions that the user must choose between rather than a single, “definitive” answer.

Elsewhere I ran experiments with *Miwo 1.0* on a short passage from a *Kirishitan-ban* text. The tool was unable to decipher a special character found in the text and produced transcriptions with a character error rate of 15.15% to 33.3% (Morris 2023, 221-222). On samples taken from other materials using *Miwo 1.0* and *Miwo 1.1*, I found character error rates of 3.28% to 36% (or 7.38% to 74.32% if we include the non-transcription of interlinear gloss) (Morris 2022).

Accuracy is not only related to erroneous transcription, but also to what a tool *can* transcribe. Sometimes tools are unable to decipher certain parts of a text or identify that characters are there. In these cases, information is lost not through developer decisions, but through technological limitations or some failure on the part of the tool. I ran some brief experiments to see how many characters are simply ignored by platforms (excluding features excluded by the developers such as glosses etc.). For a *Mitate Banzuke* of 460 characters, *Miwo* missed (failed to recognize characters existed for) 75 characters (16.3%) and *Komonjo Kamera* missed 113 characters (24.6%). For a page from an *Ōraimono*, *Miwo* missed 5 of 25 characters (20%) and *Komonjo Kamera* missed 2 (8%) though it interestingly transcribed all the gloss. Finally, for a page of a letter writing manual with text embedded in an image, *Miwo* missed 2 of 124 characters (1.6%) and *Komonjo Kamera* missed 11 (8.87%).

Conclusion

Information is lost through developer decisions of what to include and technological limitations. Reducing information loss starts with user demands for the inclusion of oft-excluded textual features such as glosses, which will encourage developers to work on the technological limitations which lie behind the exclusion of these features and challenge conceptions of these textual features as unimportant.

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Digitization work at the Finno-Ugrian Society

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The Finno-Ugrian Society, among Finland's oldest scientific societies, has a rich 140-year history of publishing on Uralic and Altaic languages and cultures. These publications encompass scholarly research, along with text collections and dictionaries, often sourced from archived handwritten materials held in Helsinki.

Digital processing of scientific texts in Uralic languages has historically presented formidable challenges. However, advancements seen last decades in Unicode coverage and text recognition technology have made it possible to handle even highly detailed phonetic transcriptions, using platforms such as Transkribus (Kahle et al. 2017; see also Partanen et al. 2021). Consequently, we have initiated the digitization of our text collections and plan to publish these materials electronically. This talk explores our current workflows and the remaining obstacles we face.

Our experiences hold significant value not only for Uralic studies but also for adjacent linguistic research traditions, as it has been customary for many languages to have extensive text collections published in the 19th and 20th centuries. From many perspectives this work is a continuation to many steps that have already been taken with these materials.

Additionally, the relations these publications have with archived primary materials, and the editorial process through which they came to be, can also be very complicated. Traditionally there have been no automatic ways to explore different published versions and original archived documents, but we are close to a point where all these sources can be digitally searched. Applying the current text recognition methods into collections such as these can improve very significantly the research use of archived documents (Muehlberger et al. 2019). Indeed, work comparable to what is discussed now has also been done with handwritten materials, and the difference between these data types, although existing, has become less critical (Partanen et al. 2022).

However, we argue that the processing of already published text collections is a particularly useful track of work, as there are enormous benefits in republishing electronically already edited and curated volumes, instead of working directly with the original materials. With the primary data the undertaking is so complex that this must be seen as a new research project, whereas the work with published collections is closer to ordinary digitalization.

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PYHFST: A Pure Python Implementation of HFST

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In this paper, we describe our work on reimplementing HFST optimized lookup on Python. Our tool is called PYHFST and it is available on GitHub (<https://github.com/Rootroo-ltd/pyhfst>), PyPi (<https://pypi.org/project/pyhfst/>) and Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org/records/7791470>).

HFST (Helsinki Finite State Transducer) (Lindén et al., 2011) is, without a doubt, one of the core technologies used in NLP for Uralic languages. It powers numerous morphological transducers for different Uralic languages (Pirinen, 2015; Trosterud et al., 2017; Kaalep et al., 2018; Rueter et al., 2021) and as such, it is an essential building block of GiellaLT (Moshagen et al., 2013), Ve'rd (Alnajjar et al., 2020) and UralicNLP (Hämäläinen, 2019) among others.

The problem, however, is that as years go by, the Python implementation of HFST has fallen behind the development. The Python package of HFST has become divided into two packages: `hfst` and `hfst-dev`. At the time of writing, the latest version of `hfst` was released in 2018 and it completely lacks support for Windows 64 and ARM-based Macs. Furthermore, it has precompiled binaries for several Python versions, out of which, 3.7 is the latest supported Python. There is a possibility of compiling the Python package from source code, but in practice this is not possible on latest Macs anymore without updating the source code.

There is a more recent version of `hfst-dev` but it mainly provides support for Linux. The most recent Python version that is supported is 3.10, but only on Linux. There is no support for any Windows version or any ARM-based systems, including latest Macs. There is no source code distribution available either, which means that the installation just fails on any unsupported platform.

Throughout history, HFST has always been a pain in the neck to install. For this reason, we undertook the challenge of porting HFST optimised lookup to pure Python. The main functionality we need is the ability to load and run HFST transducers. We took the Java implementation (Mäkelä et al., 2017) and made a quick and dirty conversion of the source code to Python using ChatGPT. The converted code did not work fully, so we spent a good amount of time debugging and optimising the code.

The biggest issue was that the pure Python version did not work fast enough. For this reason, we implemented our code in Cython as well. This makes it possible to pip install our `pyhfst` library on any system because it is pure Python. By passing an extra argument during the installation, the Cython version gets installed, which brings a massive speed boost to the library.

Pyhfst is still slower than hfst or hfst-dev. However, it is the easiest option for running HFST on Python on a modern operating system, a modern version of Python and an ARM chip. Phfst is also better than the other alternatives developed by different people in the sense that it is the only non-official Python implementation that supports both weighted and unweighted transducers.

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On searchable Mordvin corpora at the Language Bank of Finland

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This paper provides a description of the searchable Mordvin-language corpora available on the Fin-CLARIN/ Language Bank of Finland Korp server¹. First, it gives a brief background of fieldwork and literary language development that have contributed to the materials now provided or being staged as corpora in 2023. Second, it offers a brief introduction to projects that have contributed to the collection and annotation of the corpora materials. Finally, tables are given describing the Mordvin corpora in the light of other minority Uralic-language corpora, and suggestions are made for future enhancement and extensions.

In order to assess the current coverage provided by the searchable corpora, brief mention is made of the research timeline. We speak of wordlist collection (e.g., Witsen, 1705), ecclesiastical writings, early grammars (e.g., Ornatov 1838, Gabelentz 1839), collection of vernacular texts in the late 1800s (e.g., Evsev'ev 1892, Paasonen 1891, 1941), and the popularization of the Mordvin languages for the first to decades after the October

¹ <https://korp.csc.fi>

Revolution and birth of the Soviet Union (cf. Foley, 2007). Subsequent turning points in language collection and literary development are touched upon, such as the dialect collections of the 1960s (cf. OMD), the initiation of the «University of Helsinki Language Corpora Server» project (UHLCS), and the «Language Programme» initiated by the Kone Foundation in Finland.

With the background in place, we give a description of the individual corpora and their relations. Briefly, we inspect the large multilingual corpora and then the smaller corpora. Corpora with multiple languages include the National Library of Finland «Kindred Language» Pilot (2012–2015)², which brought about the initial digitization of endangered readers, non-central news and enlightenment media from the 1920s and 1930s found in Fenno-Ugrica³, the «Suki» project (Finno-Ugric Languages and the Internet)⁴, which scraped the net for Uralic language texts resulting in Wanca⁵, the Universal Dependencies UD-10⁶, corpora of manually annotated corpora, featuring here Uralic languages, Parallel Bible Verses for Uralic Studies (PaBiVUS⁷), and Electric Resource Moksha-Erzya (ERME)⁸, ERME version 2⁹, research and fieldwork texts from the Finno-Ugrian

² <https://www.kansalliskirjasto.fi/fi/projektit/sukukielten-digitointiprojekti>

³ urn:nbn:fi:lb-2014073056

⁴ <http://suki.ling.helsinki.fi/wanca/>

⁵ urn:nbn:fi:lb-2019052401

⁶ urn:nbn:fi:lb-2022061001

⁷ urn:nbn:fi:lb-2020021121

⁸ urn:nbn:fi:lb-201407306

⁹ urn:nbn:fi:lb-2023021601

Society publication series: SUS¹⁰. Smaller instances contain single book, parallel corpora, such as: a children's book about war published first in 1938: Uspenskij¹¹, a school reader for natural sciences 1939 and 1940: Tetûrev¹², a children's book portraying the ideal citizen, translated in the 1950s and 1960s: Morozov¹³, and a book providing historical information on Finland written in the 1990s: Finland Yesterday and Today¹⁴.

As most of the corpora have been automatically lemmatized and given morpho-syntactic annotations, we discuss the background of this language technological innovation, its achievements and shortcomings with regards to the Mordvin materials. This, in turn, means a brief glance at the prerequisites for finite-state morpho-lexical descriptions of many Uralic languages, e.g., «Creation of Morphological Parsers for Minority Finno-Ugrian Languages» (2013–2014) and, perhaps, the Universal Dependencies project as a source for thought in annotation conventions in the Digital Age.

Finally, we discuss the challenges for language technology. We provide tables for describing the Mordvin corpora in light of other minority Uralic-language corpora and make suggestions for future enhancement and extensions (cf., e.g., Table 1.). The challenges include: a need for more extensive and automated lemmatization and morphosyntactic annotation; a need to facilitate the use of shared metadata practices which would make it possible for the automatic or semi-automatic interchange

¹⁰ urn:nbn:fi:lb-2016092001

¹¹ urn:nbn:fi:lb-2023042426

¹² urn:nbn:fi:lb-2023042421

¹³ urn:nbn:fi:lb-2023082102

¹⁴ urn:nbn:fi:lb-2023041801

of annotation across the various corpora, preferably the former, and the need to reassess the consistency of grammatical terminology on the Uralic and World research level, e.g., the verbal moods and case.

corpus	mxx	mhr	mdf	yrk	mrj	mns	myv	udm	kca	olo	kpv	sme	krl	koi	mns
Fermo- sajala	899,106	1,662,778	617,934	1,565,429	1,029,686	925,479	497,279	NA	605,380	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
Wanaka	355,372	1,306,086	257,543	4,014	238,174	11,390	157,600	613,043	15,435	128,624	22,252	232,160	33,557	93,010	91,154
PubliSUS	395,545	NA	184,335	NA	NA	15,443	174,854	164,777	51,746	169,289	179,512	NA	174,247	24,384	NA
UD-10	17,462	NA	3,184	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	1,632	10,424	26,945	3,094	921	2,648
Lipenski	3,553	3,568	3,661	NA	3,634	4,317	NA	3,616	NA	NA	3,552	NA	NA	3,451	NA
Monsiev	28,770	16,371	14,290	NA	15,003	15,058	NA	NA	15,332	NA	14,355	NA	NA	14,613	NA
Finland	36,019	35,133	37,109	NA	NA	NA	NA	37,949	NA	NA	35,684	NA	NA	NA	NA
SUS	5,752	NA	147	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	151	NA	NA	NA	NA
Enlex	22,690	NA	22,887	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
ERME2	2,041,196	NA	855,435	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
total	3,865,665	3,623,936	1,996,525	1,569,443	1,286,497	969,687	828,793	819,385	687,893	299,545	265,930	259,065	210,898	136,379	93,862

Abbreviations

kca = Khanty, koi = Komi-Permyak, kpv = Komi-Zyrian, krl = Karelian, mdf = Moksha, mhr = Eastern & Meadow Mari, mns = Mansi, mrj = Hill Mari, myv = Erzya, olo = Olonets-Karelian (aka Livvi), sme = Northern Saami, sms = Skolt Saami, udm = Udmurt, vep = Veps, yrk = Nenets

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